

Kinetics and Mechanism of Polarographic Reduction of Orange II

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The polarographic reduction of orange II has been studied in McIlvaine buffer (subsequently referred to as McI). The electrode process is irreversible at $pH > 4$ while in more acidic solutions the process appears tending towards reversibility. The potential dependent rate constant, $k_{f,h}$ and the kinetic parameter, ' αn_a ', (the product of transfer coefficient and the number of electrons involved in the rate determining step) have been calculated. Attempt has also been made to estimate ' n_a ' and to give the mechanism of electrode process.

POLAROGRAPHY of azo-dyes including orange II has been attempted by early workers¹⁻⁴.

These studies have dealt with the determination of half-wave potentials in different pH values for the purpose of identification and variation of half-wave potentials with the substitution in benzene rings. In the present study an attempt has been made to study the kinetics of the electrode process and to give a probable mechanism of the electrode process. The above mentioned parameters have been calculated under varying conditions of pH wherever the general nature of the current voltage curves are commensurate with the quantitative calculations.

Experimental

The dropping mercury electrode (d.m.e.) consisted of a standard capillary (E. H. Sargent Co., U.S.A.). The polarographic cell was thermostated at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The d.m.e. had the following capillary characteristics $m = 1.852$ mg/sec, $t = 3.5$ sec, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 1.858$ $mg^{2/3} sec^{-1/2}$ (in $1.0M$ $NaClO_4$, at -0.60 V vs S.C.E.). The various heights of the mercury head corrected for back pressure were 34.3, 54.3, 74.3, 94.3 and 104.3 cm. $1.0M$ $NaClO_4$ was used as the supporting electrolyte. The resultant concentration of depolarizer was kept $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ in each case. Gelatin ($1 \times 10^{-2}\%$) was used as the maximum suppressor. Deoxygenation, preparation of solutions etc. were as reported earlier⁵.

Results

(i) Current-potential Curves :

Fig. 1 gives the current-voltage curves at different pH values. A sudden and significant shift in the wave towards more negative potentials is observed from pH 4 to pH 5 followed by a gradual shift in the same direction as the pH is increased. At pH 5 the wave appears to be in two parts; the main wave being preceded by a prewave.

Fig. 1. Polarograms of Orange II at different pH values, I, 2.2; II, 3.0; III, 4.0; IV, 5.0; V, 6.0; VI, 7.0; VII, 8.0.

The nature of the prewave has been ascertained from the study of current-time (c-t) curves which are shown in Fig. 2. From the inspection of these curves it is evident that a large disturbance occurs at the interface as the c-t curves are no more symmetrical (deviating from the dotted curves in Fig. 2) and are irregular. These c-t curves resemble the adsorption prewave for the adsorption of reduction product in reversible systems.

Fig. 2

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Value of 'n' :

The number of electrons involved in the electrode process is a necessary prerequisite for the mechanism and though since long for an azo group ("N=N-") it has been known^{6,7} to be 2, this was experimentally ascertained by coulometry⁸ as well as by direct determination of diffusion coefficient⁹. At all the pH values it was found to be 2 within the limits of experimental error,

Irreversibility test :

If α in relation $E_{3/4} - E_{1/4} = 0.0564/\alpha n$ (at 25°) is less than 0.5 the electrode process is said to be totally irreversible¹⁰. A more rigorous test of irreversibility depends upon the variation of limiting current upon the height of the mercury column¹¹. The results are shown in Fig. 3. This indicates that at the foot of the wave (i.e., at 0.60 volts vs S.C.E.) the limiting current is independent of height of the mercury column i.e., it is entirely determined by the rate of the electrode process while at the top of the wave (i.e., at 0.8 volts vs S.C.E.) it is independent of the rate of electrode process and is entirely determined by diffusion. And between the two extremes both rate of electrode process as well as diffusion determine the magnitude of the current. Influence of the former gradually decreases while that of latter gradually increases as one moves up the wave.

Fig. 3

Kinetic parameter :

The rate constant has been calculated by the method of Koutecky¹² and then a plot of variation of rate constant with potential in the range 0.1 < i/i_d > 0.94, yields αn_a . The results are given in Table 1

Mechanism :

In acid solution azo nitrogen takes up a proton to give a structure which is a resonance hybrid of two

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC DATA OF ORANGE II IN McILVAINE BUFFER

pH	$-E_{3/2}$	$-(E_{3/4} - E_{1/4})$	α	αn_a
	V	V		
	S.C.E.	S.C.E.		
2.2	0.035	0.025	~ 1	-
3.0	0.045	0.045	> 0.5	-
4.0	0.195	0.060	< 0.5	0.85
6.0	0.650	0.060	< 0.5	0.92
7.0	0.690	0.060	< 0.5	1.00
8.0	0.730	0.060	< 0.5	0.97

extreme structures¹³ A-A'. Grabbing of a proton makes -N=N- an electrophile. However, strong acidity may prevent dislodging of phenolic hydrogen. As the pH is increased, though still remaining acidic, this electrophilic effect probably dislodges the phenolic hydrogen as the first step to give structure B. In alkaline medium because of ionization of phenolic hydrogen the depolarizer has the resonating structure C.

The structure (A-A') is electron seeking and thus it is likely that 2 electrons are taken up in a fast reversible step

An attempt to estimate n_a from αn_a values leads to $n_a = 2$ because for irreversible system $\alpha < 0.5$. According to Meites¹⁴ only a single electron can be transferred at a time and a value of n_a exceeding 1 should merely mean that the successive steps are too nearly simultaneous to be distinguished on the time scale implicit in a polarographic measurement.

The irreversible reduction in acidic medium may be represented to occur as

In structure C because of the excess negative charge density, the electron take up is likely to be relatively difficult. Probably in the first slower step, one proton and one electron is taken up which opposes the flow of electron from the phenolic oxygen and gives as intermediate free radical which then in a fast reaction takes up another electron and proton to give the final product.

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